

Three Dimensional Modeling & Progressive Damage Analysis of Discontinuous Fibers Composites (DFC) Material

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ABSTRACT

Three dimensional modeling and progressive damage analysis of Discontinuous Fiber Composites (DFC) material called HexMC is investigated in this study. HexMC is a high performance DFC material which consists of randomly distributed strands and is ideal for high production volume of intricate geometries. Formability, low curing time and strength to weight ratio makes HexMC a prime requirement for aerospace and automotive industry. However the use of DFC is limited despite the great potential they offer due to its high heterogeneity, characterization of these materials is challenging which is crucial to design of components made from DFC. This raised the demand to developed new numerical modeling strategies to model DFC as close as possible to the actual macrostructure to reduce testing time and cost. A methodology is proposed here for three dimensional modeling of DFC, which enables to capture out of plane effects for the fact that traditional modeling approaches of HexMC cannot address. Randomization process is adopted to create statistical distributions of strands i.e. position and orientation in a pre-defined volume. With proposed modeling strategy interlaminar shear effect, waviness, out of plane orientation and stress concentration effects at the end of strand can be addressed. A Micro-Mechanics Failure based criteria (MMF) is used to predict failure in DFC by considering constituent (fiber and matrix) properties, which predicts the failure regions. Moreover, effects of mechanical loading i.e. tensile, compressive and flexure on DFC material is investigated, it is found that the overall strength properties of DFC is significantly low and highly inconsistency as compare to continuous fiber reinforced composites. The finite element results are compared with the experimental results available in the literature. Moreover, this methodology accurately predicts out of plane stress and strain distributions in DFC material.

Key Results:

DFC material macrostructure is generated in ABAQUS CAE through a python code, which generates non-intersecting network of strands with random position and orientation in a predefined volume. With the help of this model out of plane behaviors of DFC material under various loading conditions can be analyzed. Figure (Fig.1) shows macrostructure of HexMC with and without matrix, each strand is 50x8x0.15mm in dimension. Figure (Fig.2) shows stress variation in the loading direction i.e. S11 of specimen under tension and compression loading.

(a) (b)
Figure.1 HexMC macrostructure (a) Strands with matrix (Strands)

(a) (b)
Figure.2 Stress distribution (a) Stress distribution under compressive load (Mpa) (b) Stress distribution under Tensile load (Mpa)